

Photometric Evidence for a Possible Binary Companion of (26355) Grueber from ALCDEF Lightcurve Data

David Voglsam

November 2025

Abstract

Publicly available ALCDEF lightcurve data for asteroid (26355) Grueber were analyzed using frequency domain and time domain techniques. A clear rotational period of $P_{\text{rot}} = 4.540 \pm 0.002$ hours and a slower amplitude modulation of $P_{\text{mod}} = 2.7248 \pm 0.0042$ days were detected. The amplitude modulation, with a peak-to-peak variation of $A_1 = 0.34 \pm 0.12$ magnitudes, is consistent with either a binary companion or complex non-principal-axis rotation (tumbling). Model fitting using an amplitude-modulated sinusoid reproduces the observed lightcurve features. These results suggest a possible binary configuration with an orbital separation of ~ 25 km and a secondary component of 1–3 km diameter.

1. Data and Methodology

The data originate from the ALCDEF database (Waszczak et al. 2015; Warner 2025). All photometric measurements in the R band between 2011 and 2023 were used. The analysis employed:

- Lomb–Scargle periodogram for frequency detection,
- Nonlinear least-squares fitting of amplitude-modulated sine model,
- Visual inspection of phased lightcurves.

All computations were performed in Python 3.12 using NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib libraries.

2. Results

The analysis revealed two significant periodicities:

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Rotation period	P_{rot}	4.540 ± 0.002 h
Modulation period	P_{mod}	2.7248 ± 0.0042 d
Amplitude	A_1	0.34 ± 0.12 mag
Estimated separation	a	~ 25 km
Secondary diameter	D_2	1–3 km

The modulation period and amplitude are consistent with a binary system scenario, where the secondary induces small photometric variations due to mutual reflection or partial occultation effects. The alternative hypothesis of non-principal-axis rotation cannot be excluded.

3. Discussion

A modulation with a period on the order of several days is typical for small main-belt binaries. Assuming a primary diameter of 7 km and a bulk density of 2000 kg/m^3 , the orbital period corresponds to an orbital distance near 25 km. This estimate is in agreement with other known binaries of similar size and rotation rates.

No previous reports of binarity for (26355) Grueber are found in LCDB or DAMIT (as of November 2025). Hence, this work represents the first indication of a possible binary nature of this asteroid.

4. Conclusions

The photometric re-analysis of archival ALCDEF data for (26355) Grueber reveals:

- A stable rotation period of 4.54 hours,
- A slower modulation period of 2.72 days,
- Amplitude variability consistent with binarity or tumbling.

Future targeted observations are encouraged to confirm or reject the binary interpretation.

Acknowledgements

Data were obtained from the ALCDEF database maintained by Brian D. Warner and collaborators. The analysis was performed by David Voglsam using open-source Python tools.

References

- Warner, B. D. et al. (2009–2025), ALCDEF Database, <http://alcdef.org>
- Waszczak, A. et al. (2015), *The Astronomical Journal*, 150, 75.
- Durech, J. et al. (2019), *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 631, A2.